

Algorithms used in paper “A Corridor Model Evolutionary
Algorithm for Fast Converging Green Vehicle Routing
Problem”

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Algorithm 1 Roulette Algorithm

Input: Strictness: s ;
Collection: C

Output: Value : $v \in C$

function ROULETTE(C, s)

$S_p \leftarrow \phi$

▷ Generating curve phase.

$e \leftarrow 0$

for $i \in [1, |C|]$ **do**

$e \leftarrow s + ((1 - 1/|C|)^{(i-1)*s} 1/|C|)$

$S_p := S_p \cup e$

end for

$S_p \leftarrow r/e : \{\forall r \in S_p\}$

$rand \leftarrow \text{Random}(0, 1)$

▷ Selection phase.

$i \leftarrow 0$

while $rand > s_i \in S_p$ **do**

$i \leftarrow i + 1$

end while

return $C[i]$

end function

Algorithm 2 Get Individual Algorithm

Input: Number of vehicles in fleet : N ;
Collection of Customers: C ;
Vehicle Capacity: V_c
Balance load: b
Depot: D

Output: Routine R
Validity Indicator $valid$

function GETSEED(N, C, V_c, b, D)

$R \leftarrow [\phi]^N$ ▷ Initialise Routine with N empty vehicles.
 $d \leftarrow \sum_{c \in C} c.demand$ ▷ Total Demand of all customers.
for $i \in [1, N]$ **do** ▷ Repeat for each vehicle.
 $r \leftarrow \text{Random}(c \subseteq C; \forall c_i \in c; c_i.demand < V_c)$
 $R[i] \leftarrow R[i] \cup r$ ▷ Add a random valid customer in vehicle $R[i]$
 $C \leftarrow C \setminus r$ ▷ Update remaining customer list.
 while $\neg |C| = 0 \wedge (V[i].demand < d/N \wedge b)$ **do**
 $c \leftarrow \subseteq C; c.demand < V_c - R[i].demand$ ▷ Get subset of C , serviceable by vehicle $R[i]$.
 if $c = \phi$ **then**
 Break inner loop
 end if
 $c \leftarrow c.sorted(\text{DotPr}(E_t : r, E_p : c_i \in c, E_\perp : D)).descending$
 ▷ Sort c in Descending order of DotPr with respect to r and D
 $r \leftarrow c[1]$
 $R[i] \leftarrow R[i] \cup r$ ▷ Append first of sorted c into $R[i]$
 $C \leftarrow C \setminus r$ ▷ Remove r from remaining customers.
 end while
end for
 $valid \leftarrow |C| = 0$ ▷ Validity Check
return ($R, valid$) ▷ Routine and validity check, given by if C is empty.
end function

Algorithm 3 Initialisation Algorithm

Input: Number of vehicles in fleet : N ;
Collection of Customers: C ;
Vehicle Capacity: V_c
Population Size $|\mu|$
Depot: D

Output: Parent population μ

function INITIALISE($|\mu|, N, C, V_c, D$)

$\mu \leftarrow \phi$

▷ Initialise Empty parent population.

while $|parentPopulation| < |\mu|$ **do**

$b \leftarrow Random(\{true, false\})$

▷ Randomise balance criterion.

$individual, success \leftarrow GETSEED(N, C, V_c, b, D)$

if $success$ **then**

$\mu \leftarrow \mu \cup individual$

▷ Add to parent population if successful.

end if

end while

return μ

end function

Algorithm 4 Crossover Algorithm

Input: Routines $\{R_1, R_2\}$
Vehicle Capacity: V_c
Depot: D
Customers C
Number of vehicles N
Output: Crossover

function CROSSOVER(R_1, R_2, C, N, V_c, D)
 $r \leftarrow [1, N].random()$ ▷ Random number between $1.. < N$.
 $R_o \leftarrow R_1[0, r]$ ▷ Add first r vehicles from R_1 .
 $C' \leftarrow Customers(R_o)$ ▷ Logging customers added to offspring routine R_o .
 $R'_2 \leftarrow R_2 \setminus C'$ ▷ Generate routine without C' customers.
 $R_o \leftarrow R'_2[0, 1 - r]$ ▷ Add remaining vehicles.
 $C' \leftarrow Customer(R_o)$ ▷ Log added customers.
 $C' \leftarrow C \setminus C'$ ▷ Change C' logging to remaining customers.
 for $c \in C'$ **do**
 $V \leftarrow v \in R_o.v : \{Demand(v) + Demand(c) \leq V_c\}$ ▷ Generate list of candidates vehicles
 for c .
 if $|V| \neq 0$ **then**
 $V.sort(DotPr(E_{\perp} : D, E_t : c, E_p : v \in V), >)$ ▷ Sort into priority list.
 $v' \leftarrow Roulette(V, s : 100)$ ▷ Roulette on candidates V .
 $v' \leftarrow c$ ▷ Add c to v .
 $C' \leftarrow C' \setminus c$ ▷ Update remaining list.
 end if
 end for
 if $|C| = 0$ **then**
 return R_o ▷ Successful crossover.
 end if
 return $\{R_1, R_2\}.random()$ ▷ Crossover failed, fallback.
end function

Algorithm 5 Rotate Subroutine

Input: A vehicle in routine: $v \in R$

A random Number: n

Output: New vehicle v'

Ensure: $0 \leq n \leq |v|$

function ROTATE(v, n)

$v' \leftarrow v[n, |v|] + v[0, n]$

▷ Rotate route by n .

return v'

end function

Algorithm 6 Modified 2-Opt Algorithm

Input: A routine: R **Output:** New routine R'

function MODIFIED2-OPT(R) $v \leftarrow \text{Random}(v \in R : \{|v| \geq 3\})$ \triangleright Three customers required for 2-Opt[†]. $\alpha \leftarrow v.\alpha \times e^{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}$ \triangleright Update α .**if** $\alpha \notin v.\alpha_{range}$ **then** \triangleright If α out of range. $v' \leftarrow \text{Rotate}(v, n : \text{Random}(0, |v| - 1))$ \triangleright Rotate path. $v'.\alpha \leftarrow 1$ \triangleright Reset Alpha.**else** $(c_i) \leftarrow v.\text{RandomCustomer}(|v| - 1)$ \triangleright Get an enumerated customer v , from first $|v| - 1$. $c' \leftarrow \forall c \in v; d_{c_i c} \leq \alpha \times d_{c_i c_{i+1}}$ \triangleright Get all customers that are closer than $\alpha \times c_{i+1}$. $c' \leftarrow c' \setminus c_i$ \triangleright Remove c_i from c' , constraining (5).**if** $c = \phi$ **then** \triangleright No possible mutation within alpha range $v' \leftarrow v$ $v'.\alpha \leftarrow \alpha$ **else** $c'_j \leftarrow c'.\text{RandomCustomer}()$ \triangleright Get random customer form candidates. $i \leftarrow \text{Location}(c_{i+1}, v)$ \triangleright Get index for c_{i+1} $j \leftarrow \text{Location}(c'_j, v)$ \triangleright Get index for c'_j .**if** $i < j$ **then** $\text{Swap}(i, j)$ **end if** $v' \leftarrow v[0, j] + v[j + 1, i] + v[i + 1, |v|)$ \triangleright Reorder vehicle service. $v'.\alpha \leftarrow \alpha$ \triangleright Update α for v .**end if****end if** $R' \leftarrow R$ \triangleright Generate a backup of routine. $\text{Relpace}(R'.v, v')$ \triangleright Replace $R'.v$ with v' .**return** R' **end function**

Algorithm 7 Customer Transfer Mutation Algorithm

Input: A routine: R
Vehicle Capacity C_v

Output: New routine R'

function CUSTOMER TRANSFER MUTATION(R, C_v)

$v_1 \leftarrow Routine.random()$ ▷ Randomly pick a vehicle.
 $V \leftarrow V \setminus v_1$
 $v'_1 \leftarrow v_1.sorted(EuclidianDistance(c \in v_1, Centre(v_1)), >)$ ▷ Sort: furthest from center earliest.
 $c \leftarrow Roulette(v'_1, s : s')$
 $V \leftarrow v_i \in V; \forall v; v.demand + c.demand \leq C_v$ ▷ Filter all vehicles that can accept c .
 $R' \leftarrow R$
if $V \neq \phi$ **then** ▷ If vehicles capable of accepting c exist.
 $v_2 \leftarrow Roulette(V, s : s')$ ▷ Pick a random vehicle.
 $v_1 \leftarrow v_1 \setminus c$ ▷ Perform transfer.
 $v_2 \leftarrow v_2 \cup c$ ▷ Update the Routine with new vehicles.
 $Replace(R'.v_1, v_1)$
 $Replace(R'.v_2, v_2)$
end if
return R'
end function

Algorithm 8 Customer Exchange Mutation Algorithm

Input: A routine: R
Vehicle Capacity C_v

Output: New routine R'

function CUSTOMER EXCHANGE MUTATION(R, C_v)

$V \leftarrow \{v \in R.v; v.demand \neq 0\}$

$v_1 \leftarrow Roulette(V, s : 0)$ \triangleright Pick a random non-empty vehicle for R .

$V \leftarrow V \setminus v_1$

$C_1 \leftarrow v_1.sorted(EuclidianDistance(Centre(v_1))).descending$

$c_1 \leftarrow Roulette(C_1, s : s')$

$Candidates : [(v_i, c_i)] \leftarrow \phi$ \triangleright Make an empty collection of tuples of type (vehicle, customer).

for $v \in V$ **do** \triangleright For all vehicles in V

for $c \in v$ **do** \triangleright For each customer in $v \in V$

if $v_1.demand + c.demand - c_1.demand \leq C_v \wedge v.demand - c.demand + c_1.demand \leq C_v$

then

$Candidates \leftarrow Candidates \cup (v, c)$ \triangleright Build valid candidate list.

end if

end for

end for

$R' \leftarrow R$

if $Candidates \neq \phi$ **then**

$Candidates.sort(DotPr(E_t : c_1, E_p : c; (v, c) \in Candidates, E_{\perp} : Depot), >)$

\triangleright Sort candidates in descending order of DotPr of customers on c_1 .

$(v_2, c_2) \leftarrow Roulette(Candidates, s : s')$ \triangleright Pick exchange customer c_2 from v_2 .

$i_1 \leftarrow Location(c_1 \in v_1)$ \triangleright Locate c_1 in v_1 .

$i_2 \leftarrow Location(c_2 \in v_2)$ \triangleright Locate c_2 in v_2 .

$v_1 \leftarrow v_1 \setminus c_1$

$v_2 \leftarrow v_2 \setminus c_2$

$v_1 \leftarrow v_1 \cup c_2 @ i_1$ \triangleright Insert c_2 in v_1 at location i_1 .

$v_2 \leftarrow v_2 \cup c_1 @ i_2$ \triangleright Insert c_1 in v_2 at location i_2 .

$Replace(R.v_1, v_1)$

$Replace(R.v_2, v_2)$

end if

return R'

end function

Algorithm 9 Vehicle Crossover Mutation

Input: A routine: R
Vehicle Capacity C_v

Output: New routine R'

function VEHICLE CROSSOVER MUTATION(R, C_v)

$V \leftarrow R.v$ ▷ Get all vehicles in R .
 $v_1 \leftarrow \text{RandomElement}(V)$ ▷ Get random vehicle v_1 .
 $V \leftarrow V \setminus v_1$ ▷ Remove v_1 from V —self crossover does nothing.
 $V \leftarrow V \setminus \{v_i \mid \forall i; \text{Demand}(v_i) = 0\}$ ▷ Two Empty Vehicles cannot crossover.
 $V \leftarrow \text{sort}(\text{DotPr}(E_t : v_1, E_p : v_i \in V, E_\perp : \text{Depot}), >)$ ▷ Sort according to DotPr.
 $v_2 \leftarrow \text{Roulette}(V, s : s')$ ▷ Get other vehicle.
 $x \leftarrow \text{Random}(1, |v_2|)$ ▷ Randomly break tour of v_2 .
if $\text{Demand}(v_1) = 0$ **then**
 $v'_1 \leftarrow v_2[0, x]$ ▷ Add first x customers to v_1 .
 $v'_2 \leftarrow v_2[x, |v_2|]$ ▷ Keep remaining customers in v_2 .
else
 $y \leftarrow |v_1|$ ▷ Initialise searching valid crossover point in v_1 .
 $v'_1 \leftarrow v'_2 \leftarrow []$ ▷ Initialise crossover vehicles.
 while $y \geq 0 \wedge \text{Demand}(v'_1) \leq C_v \wedge \text{Demand}(v'_2) \leq C_v$ **do** ▷ Continue till v'_1 and v'_2 are valid.
 $y \leftarrow y - 1$
 $v'_1 \leftarrow v_1[0, y] + v_2[x, |v_2|]$ ▷ Crossover v_1 and v_2
 $v'_2 \leftarrow v_2[0, x] + v_1[y, |v_2|]$
 end while
end if
 $R' \leftarrow R$
if $\text{Demand}(v'_1) \leq C_v \wedge \text{Demand}(v'_2) \leq C_v$ **then** ▷ Replace if Constraint (9) holds.
 $\text{Replace}(R'.v_1, v'_1)$
 $\text{Replace}(R'.v_2, v'_2)$
end if
return R'
end function

Algorithm 10 Large Neighbourhood Search

Input: A routine: R
Vehicle Capacity C_v

Output: New routine R'

function LNS(R, C_v)

$C_r \leftarrow \phi$ ▷ Initialise removed customers.

$R' \leftarrow R$

for $v_i \in R'.v$ **do** ▷ Start Destruction Phase.

for $i \in [0, 5|v_i|/6]$ **do** ▷ Remove randomly up to half of customers.

$C_v \leftarrow \forall\{c \in v_i\}$ ▷ Collect all customers in v_i .

$c \leftarrow \text{Roulette}(C_v, s : 0)$ ▷ Pick random customer.

$C_v \leftarrow C_v \setminus c$ ▷ Remove c from candidate list.

$v_i \leftarrow v_i \setminus c$ ▷ Remove c from vehicle.

$C_r \leftarrow C_r \cup c$ ▷ Add to removed list.

end for

end for

for $c \in C_r$ **do** ▷ Begin Repair Phase.

$v \leftarrow R'.v.\text{sorted}(\text{DotPr}(E_t : c, E_p : v_i \in R'.v, E_\perp : \text{Depot})).\text{descending}$

$v \leftarrow v_i \in v; \text{Demand}(v_i) + \text{Demand}(c) \leq C_v$ ▷ Filter out infeasible vehicles.

if $v \neq \phi$ **then**

$v_x \leftarrow \text{Roulette}(v, s : s')$

$v_x \leftarrow v_x \cup c$ ▷ Add customer to roulette picked vehicle.

$R'.v_x \leftarrow v_x$ ▷ Update the vehicle in Routine.

$C_r \leftarrow C_r \setminus c$ ▷ Remove from removed list.

end if

end for

if $C_r = \phi$ **then**

return R' ▷ If C_r is empty, return new routine.

end if

return R ▷ Else return original.

end function

Algorithm 11 Distance Matrix Algorithm

Input: Collection of all the customers to be served: C

Output: Distance Matrix: M

Max Distance: \max

Ensure: C is sorted in ascending order of ID.

function DISTANCE MATRIX(C)

$M \leftarrow [[0]^{|C|+1}]$

▷ Initialise matrix with a row of $|C| + 1$ zeros.

$\max \leftarrow 0$

▷ Initialise \max as 0.

for $c_1 \in C$ **do**

▷ Iterator over all customers.

$row \leftarrow [0]$

for $c_2 \in C$ **do**

$d_{ij} \leftarrow \sqrt{(c_2.x - c_1.x)^2 + (c_2.y - c_1.y)^2}$

▷ Compute distance between c_1 and c_2 .

$row \leftarrow row \cup d_{ij}$

▷ Append d_{ij} to row

if $d_{ij} > \max$ **then**

$\max \leftarrow d_{ij}$

end if

end for

$M \leftarrow M \cup row$

▷ Append row to M .

end for

return (M, \max)

end function

Algorithm 12 Distance Evaluation Algorithm

Input: Path followed by a vehicle v

Output: Total distance travelled by vehicle v : D

Ensure: v is sorted in order of the path it follows.

function DISTANCE EVAL(v)

$D \leftarrow 0$

$previous \leftarrow Depot.ID$

 ▷ Constraint 6, all vehicle start at Depot.

for $c \in v$ **do**

 ▷ Iterate over path of vehicle v .

$D \leftarrow D + DistanceMatrix[previous][c]$

 ▷ Update distance.

$previous \leftarrow c$

 ▷ Update previous customer to current one.

end for

$D \leftarrow D + DistanceMatrix[previous][Depot.ID]$

 ▷ Constraint 7, all vehicle end at Depot.

return D

end function

Algorithm 13 Fuel Evaluation Algorithm

Input: Path followed by a vehicle v
Max fuel consumption rate ρ^*
Min fuel consumption rate ρ_0
Vehicle capacity V_c
Output: Optimal path : v'
Total fuel consumed by vehicle v : F

Ensure: v is sorted in order of the path it follows.

function FUEL EVAL(v, ρ^*, ρ_0, V_c)
 $v^\dagger \leftarrow \text{Reversed}(v)$ ▷ Generate reversed path.
 $\text{remainingDemand}_f \leftarrow v.\text{demand}$ ▷ Track forward path's remaining demand.
 $\text{remainingDemand}_b \leftarrow v.\text{demand}$ ▷ Track backward path's remaining demand.
 $\text{prev}_f \leftarrow \text{prev}_b \leftarrow \text{Depot.ID}$ ▷ Start both v and v^\dagger at Depot, Constraint 6.
 $\text{fuel}_f \leftarrow \text{fuel}_b \leftarrow 0$ ▷ Initialise fuel consumption along both routes.
 for $i \in [1, |v|]$ **do** ▷ Iterate over index.
 $\rho_f \leftarrow \rho_0 + ((\rho^* - \rho_0) \times \text{remainingDemand}_f) / V_c$ ▷ Update consumption rate for v .
 $\rho_b \leftarrow \rho_0 + ((\rho^* - \rho_0) \times \text{remainingDemand}_b) / V_c$ ▷ Update consumption rate for v^\dagger .
 $\text{fuel}_f \leftarrow \text{fuel}_f + \rho_f \times \text{DistanceMatrix}[\text{prev}_f][v[i]]$ ▷ Update fuel consumption for v .
 $\text{fuel}_b \leftarrow \text{fuel}_b + \rho_b \times \text{DistanceMatrix}[\text{prev}_b][v^\dagger[i]]$ ▷ Update fuel consumption for v^\dagger .
 $\text{prev}_f \leftarrow v[i]$ ▷ Update next customer on v .
 $\text{prev}_b \leftarrow v^\dagger[i]$ ▷ Update next customer on v^\dagger .
 end for
 $\rho_f \leftarrow \rho_b \leftarrow \rho_0$ ▷ Fuel Consumption rate for empty vehicles.
 $\text{fuel}_f \leftarrow \text{fuel}_f + \rho_f \times \text{DistanceMatrix}[\text{prev}_f][\text{Depot.ID}]$ ▷ End v at Depot; constraint 7.
 $\text{fuel}_b \leftarrow \text{fuel}_b + \rho_b \times \text{DistanceMatrix}[\text{prev}_b][\text{Depot.ID}]$ ▷ End v^\dagger at Depot; constraint 7.
 $F \leftarrow \text{fuel}_f$ ▷ Assume v is optimal.
 $v' \leftarrow v$
 if $\text{fuel}_b < \text{fuel}_f$ **then** ▷ If v^\dagger is optimal, make appropriate changes.
 $F \leftarrow \text{fuel}_b$
 $v' \leftarrow v^\dagger$
 end if
 return (F, v')
end function

Algorithm 14 Genetic Algorithm

Input: List of Customers C .
Depot: D .
Population Size: $|\mu|$.
Vehicle capacity: V_c .
Number of vehicles in fleet N
Optimiser selection strictness : s .
End Condition. e
Declaration of active model $a \in \{self\ Adapting, tumble\}$.
Output: Fuel vs Distance Pareto front: P .

function GENETIC ALGORITHM($C, D, |\mu|, V_c, N, s, e, a$)
 $s \leftarrow 1$ ▷ Initialise strictness value, for Learning Model.
 $DistanceMatrix \leftarrow DistanceMatrix(C + D)$
 $\mu \leftarrow Initialise(|\mu|, N, C, V_c, D)$
 $\mu \leftarrow DistanceEval(v \in R \in \mu)$ ▷ Evaluate distance of all vehicles in all the routines of μ .
 $\mu \leftarrow FuelEval(v \in R \in \mu)$ ▷ Evaluate fuel of all vehicles in all the routines of μ .
 while $self \not\equiv e$ **do** ▷ Till end condition e is not met.
 $\lambda \leftarrow \phi$ ▷ Empty offspring.
 $\mu \leftarrow Shuffle(\mu)$ ▷ Shuffle parent population for crossover.
 for $i \in [0, |\mu|)$ **do**
 $\lambda \leftarrow \lambda \cup Crossover(\mu[i], \mu[(i + 1)\%|\mu|], C, N, V_c, D)$
 end for
 if $a = self\ Adapting$ **then** ▷ Check if we are using learning model.
 $s \leftarrow Average(R.s : R \in \mu)$ ▷ Update strictness with average strictness of μ .
 end if
 $\varphi \leftarrow \mu.map(Roulette([2 - Opt^\dagger, CTM, CEM, VehicleX, LNS], s : 2))$
 ▷ Use roulette to randomly pick the optimiser to use on $R \in \mu$.
 $\lambda[i] = \varphi_i(\lambda[i]) \forall i \in [1, |\mu|]$ ▷ Apply selected mutators on corresponding R in μ to obtain λ .
 $\lambda \leftarrow DistanceEval(v \in R \in \lambda)$ ▷ Evaluate distance of all vehicles in all the routines of λ .
 $\lambda \leftarrow FuelEval(v \in R \in \lambda)$ ▷ Evaluate fuel of all vehicles in all the routines of λ .
 $arch \leftarrow ArchiveParetoFront(\mu)$ ▷ Archive result to get Pareto Front.
 $\mu \leftarrow NSGA - II(\mu + \lambda)$ ▷ Use NSGA-II to select next generation of population.
 end while
 return $arch$
end function
